

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN: 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**

SJIF Impact Factor: 7.187

Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

**EVALUATION OF LEVEL OF MICRO NUTRIENTS IN THE
BRAIN TUMOR PATIENTS**Dr. Muhammad Junaid¹, Dr. Muhammad Ahsan¹, Dr. Ameer Hamza¹¹Jinnah Hospital Lahore**Article Received:** May 2020**Accepted:** June 2020**Published:** July 2020**Abstract:**

Introduction: According to estimates from the International Agency for Research on Cancer (IARC), there were 14.1 million new cancer cases in 2012 worldwide, of which 8 million occurred in economically developing countries, which contain about 82% of the world's population. **Objectives of the study:** This study was designed to evaluate the status of macronutrients such as Ca and Fe and micronutrients such as Cu, Zn and Se in brain tumor patients. **Methodology of the study:** This descriptive study was conducted in Jinnah Hospital Lahore during January 2019 to July 2019. The patient who were come at hospital for treatment, selected for this study. **Results:** The analysis of blood micro and macro nutrients shows that there is a huge difference in control group and patients. **Conclusion:** It is concluded that quality of life is very much important in brain tumor therapies. The level of nutrients become decreases due to tumor that's why it is necessary to maintain the normal values of nutrients. So that patient may survive better quality life.

Corresponding author:**Dr. Muhammad Junaid,**
Jinnah Hospital Lahore

QR code

Please cite this article in press Muhammad Junaid et al, Evaluation Of Level Of Micro Nutrients In The Brain Tumor Patients., Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2020; 07(07).

INTRODUCTION:

According to estimates from the International Agency for Research on Cancer (IARC), there were 14.1 million new cancer cases in 2012 worldwide, of which 8 million occurred in economically developing countries, which contain about 82% of the world's population¹. The most widely recognized kinds of danger incorporate colorectal malignancy, lung disease, and, contingent upon sexual orientation, bosom or prostate tumor². The relating gauges for add up to growth passages in 2012 were 8.2 million. By 2030, the worldwide weight is relied upon to develop to 21.7 million new tumor cases and 13 million malignancy passing's just because of the development and maturing of the populace³. Be that as it may, the evaluated future malignancy weight will most likely be extensively bigger because of the reception of ways of life that are known to expand tumor hazard, for example, less than stellar eating routine, physical inertia, and smoking. Growths identified with these variables, for example, bosom, lung, and colorectal tumors, are as of now on the ascent in financially progressing nations⁴.

Alexandra, (2000) talked about in his paper the rate of cerebrum tumors is expanding quickly, especially in the more seasoned populace⁵. Advances in atomic science help to clarify contrasts in biologic conduct and reaction to treatment of mind tumors in the elderly contrasted and more youthful patients. The quantity of elderly patients who want and get treatment for mind tumors and are incorporated into clinical trials is expanding. This article surveys the writing on the study of disease transmission, clinical perspectives, and treatment of mind tumors, with accentuation on the more established patient populace⁶. The expanded rate of cerebrum tumors in the elderly is primarily because of the expanding number of individuals who contain the more established populace. Age and execution status are critical autonomous prognostic pointers, together with tumor histology. Medical procedure, radiation treatment, and chemotherapy can profit elderly patients with mind tumors with great histologies, tumor area, and great execution status⁷. The reaction rates to accessible treatments are less great than in more youthful patients, and just few elderly patients are enlisted in clinical investigations tending to new treatment modalities. Cerebrum tumors in the

elderly have particular attributes that decide their biologic conduct and reaction to treatment. There is a requirement for clinical investigations intended for treatment of cerebrum tumors in more established patients, and prerequisites for restoration and emotionally supportive networks for the elderly should be tended to⁸.

Objectives of the study

This study was designed to evaluate the status of macronutrients such as Ca and Fe and micronutrients such as Cu, Zn and Se in brain tumor patients.

METHODOLOGY OF THE STUDY:

This descriptive study was conducted in Jinnah Hospital Lahore during January 2019 to July 2019. The patient who were come at hospital for treatment, selected for this study. The confirmed cases of brain tumor were selected for this course of study. This study was conducted by the approval of ethical committee and with the permission of patients. We collect the 5cc blood sample of patients for the analysis of micronutrients in brain tumor patients. Commercially available kits were used for the analysis of micronutrients in the blood of patients. Blood samples will be collected into EDTA tubes from fasting proteins. The blood will be centrifuged and indomethacin and butylated hydroxytoluene will be added into the plasma samples before they will be stored at -80°C until analysis.

Statistical analysis

Student's t-test was performed to evaluate the differences in roughness between group P and S. Two-way ANOVA was performed to study the contributions. A chi-square test was used to examine the difference in the distribution of the fracture modes (SPSS 19.0 for Windows, SPSS Inc., USA).

RESULTS:

The analysis of blood micro and macro nutrients shows that there is a huge difference in control group and patients. The level of nutrients is decreases in patients as compared to control and healthy group. The low levels of nutrients show that it leads to many deformities also. With so many things going on while battling a brain tumor, it's challenging to pay attention to nutrition.

Table 01: Statistical analysis of micro and macro nutrients of patients and control group

Group Statistics					
	group	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Vit_A	control	10	1.9743	91.729355	29.007369
	patients	17	7.89106	69.624623	16.886451
Vit_C	control	10	2.41350	1.242764	.392996
	patients	17	1.06559	.386902	.093838
Vit_E	control	10	8.33150	.946245	.299229
	patients	17	2.47400	.798902	.193762
Zn	control	10	9.71250	11.703929	3.701107
	patients	16	6.16988	21.376463	5.344116
Fe	control	10	8.89530E1	3.331970	1.053661
	patients	16	9.10994E1	14.039887	3.509972
Mn	control	10	6.40500	1.709121	.540472
	patients	16	5.20250	1.391165	.347791
Se	control	10	6.55662E1	20.104143	6.357488
	patients	16	6.65813	1.943839	.485960
Cu	control	10	7.72700	3.199792	1.011863
	patients	16	8.75406E1	19.200278	4.800070

DISCUSSION:

It is the highly invasive nature of malignant brain tumors that makes them difficult to manage using most conventional therapies. Although restricted ketogenic diets can be effective in managing invasive brain cancer in children and adults, few studies have evaluated the therapeutic effect of calorie or dietary restriction on invasive brain cancer in mice⁹⁻¹⁰.

Several issues can complicate attempts to implement metabolic diet therapy for brain cancer management in patients¹¹. Availability of a drug that would mimic the global therapeutic effects of dietary energy restriction would certainly be the easiest way to implement the therapy. However, no drugs are known that can simultaneously lower glucose levels while elevating ketones in the absence of some form of calorie restriction, though the recently described ketone ester diets could be an exception¹².

CONCLUSION:

It is concluded that quality of life is very much important in brain tumor therapies. The level of nutrients become decreases due to tumor that's why it is necessary to maintain the normal values of nutrients. So that patient may survive better quality life.

REFERENCES:

1. Leighton C, Fisher B, Bauman G, et al. Supratentorial low-grade glioma in adults: an analysis of prognostic factors and timing of radiation. *J Clin Oncol*. 1997;15:1294–1301.
2. Mainio A, Hakko H, Timonen M, Niemela A, Koivukangas J, Rasanen P. Depression in

relation to survival among neurosurgical patients with a primary brain tumor: a 5-year follow-up study. *Neurosurgery*. 2005;56:1234–1242.

3. Imperato JP, Paleologos NA, Vick NA. Effects of treatment on long-term survivors with malignant astrocytomas. *Ann Neurol*. 1990;28:818–822.
4. Leibel SA, Gutin PH, Wara WM, et al. Survival and quality of life after interstitial implantation of removable high-activity iodine-125 sources for the treatment of patients with recurrent malignant gliomas. *Int J Radiat Oncol Biol Phys*. 1989;17:1129–1139.
5. National Cancer Institute. Surveillance, Epidemiology, and End Results program public-use data, 1973–1998. Rockville, MD: National Cancer Institute, Division of Cancer Control and Population Sciences, Surveillance Research Program, Cancer Statistics Branch; 2001.
6. Schantz SP, Spitz MR, Hsu TC. Mutagen sensitivity in patients with head and neck cancers: a biologic marker for risk of multiple primary malignancies. *J Natl Cancer Inst*. 1990;82(22):1773–5.
7. Regezi JA, Dekker NP, Ramos DM, Li X, Macabeo-Ong M, Jordan RC. Proliferation and invasion factors in HIV-associated dysplastic and nondysplastic oral warts and in oral squamous cell carcinoma: an immunohistochemical and RT-PCR evaluation. *Oral Surg Oral Med Oral Pathol Oral Radiol Endod*. 2002;94(6):724–31.
8. Silverman S, Jr, Gorsky M, Lozada F. Oral leukoplakia and malignant transformation. A

- follow-up study of 257 patients. *Cancer*. 1984;53(3):563–8.
9. Jullien JA, Downer MC, Speight PM, Zakrzewska JM. Evaluation of health care workers' accuracy in recognizing oral cancer and pre-cancer. *Int Dent J*. 1996;46(4):334–9.
 10. Nagao T, Ikeda N, Fukano H, Miyazaki H, Yano M, Warnakulasuriya S. Outcome following a population screening programme for oral cancer and precancer in Japan. *Oral Oncol*. 2000;36(4):340–6.
 11. Sankaranarayanan R, Ramadas K, Thomas G, Muwonge R, Thara S, Mathew B, et al. Effect of screening on oral cancer mortality in Kerala, India: a cluster-randomised controlled trial. *Lancet*. 2005;365(9475):1927–33.
 12. Yu BK, Kuo BI, Yen MS, Twu NF, Lai CR, Chen PJ, et al. Improved early detection of cervical intraepithelial lesions by combination of conventional Pap smear and speculscopy. *Eur J Gynaecol Oncol*. 2003;24(6):495–9.